

The Role of Religion in Shaping Morality for National Integration

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Abstract

In achieving national integration in Nigeria, several efforts have been put in place by leaders since the independence of the nation in 1960. Concerted moves have been deployed to see that policies and programmes that can engender national integration succeed, yet, all to no avail. The anticipated cohesion of the nation remains endangered with all sorts of socio-cultural and political differences that permeates all the fabrics of the country. This lacuna must be resolved with urgency or else, the indivisibility and oneness of Nigeria will remain a mirage. Hence, this problem is what this paper is out to solve. This paper utilized descriptive method and argues that religion as a factor in the modification of moral life, provides deterrent for the moral obligations and responsibilities to the adherents. The bedrock for virtues of self-discipline, prudence, wisdom, courage, gratitude, goodness, purity, kindness, compassion, mercy, generosity, dedication to duty, brotherliness and many more is religion which is to invariably build a platform for nation integration when there are mutual and cordial relationship among the people. The researcher believes that it is possible to achieve national integration if ethnicity, nepotism, corruption, bad political leadership are jettison and sound religious values are allowed to shape the morality of the people.

Keywords: Religion, national integration, religious values, Nigeria, morality

Introduction

Nigeria is a country with a diversity of religious traditions, including Christianity, Islam, and African religions. The two main religious communities in Nigeria are Christianity and Islam due to their sizes. Both of these religions emphasize moral behavior and the idea of rewards and penalties for followers and non-followers. The intersection of religion and morality has been the subject of extensive scholarly writing. It is widely accepted that religion serves as the unquestionable basis for morality and acts as its primary determinant. In other words, morality cannot exist without religion. One of the commonly acknowledged elements required for nation-building in any given period of history is religion as a crucial means of providing morality.

However, in recent years, a lack of morality has resulted in an increase in moral decadence, as evidenced by social vices such as nepotism, stealing, violence, prostitution, armed robbery, kidnapping, teen pregnancy, and infidelity in marriage, among others, that are endangering Nigeria's national integration. These social practices posed a serious obstacle to national growth and cohesion. In actuality, Nigeria's history has been marked by a wide range of moral dilemmas that have seriously hampered national integration. The moral crises have in no small part fueled citizen disunity and division. As a result, the aforementioned absence of ethical standards highlights the crucial role that religion plays in helping citizens cultivate moral qualities necessary for national cohesion.

Since religion is ingrained in men and affects practically every element of society, it plays a crucial role in national integration. In this situation, if every religious organization defends morally sound beliefs, preaches them to their followers, and upholds them, it will foster moral virtues such as love, peace, justice, tolerance, dedication, and self-control among others, virtues that are essential for national integration. It is on this background that this study examines the role of religion in shaping morality for national integration. To have a progressive discussion the study will examine basic concepts underlining the objectives of the paper. These are the concept of Religion, Morality, and national Integration. The study will also examine religious role in shaping morality in Nigeria as well as religious moral values exploitable for national integration.

Conceptual Clarification of Terms

Religion

Religion has been defined from various perspectives such as sociology, anthropology, phenomenology and theology. However, religion in the African perspective, according to Bolaji Idowu, “originated from man’s spontaneous awareness of a living power, wholly other and infinitely greater than himself, a power of mystery because unseen yet a present and urgent reality, seeking to bring man into communion with Himself.”¹ This definition emphasizes man’s recognition of a reality greater than himself and his efforts to establish a peaceful connection with that Reality. In this situation, according to Gideon Oshitelu, quoting James, “religion is man’s effective desire to be in the appropriate relations with a sacred transcendental order directing human destinies and natural events in life that finds expressions in a specified system of ritual and belief.”²

According to this perspective, religion is an attempt by humans to have a harmonious relationship with the Supreme Being in charge of human destiny. In essence, religion is the means through which people express an understanding of the reality and meaning of life. It is thought that religion has a significant impact on how individuals and groups view ethical principles and morals. Religion has made significant impacts on the social, spiritual and political affairs of the country. The high esteem given to religion is demonstrated by the diverse manner through which it is carried out in many societies. It serves as the social glue that holds the community together and serves as a stabilizing influence in society. It is a powerful force for fostering morality and society.

Morality

The word moral comes from the Latin *moralis*, which also implies manners or customs. The term may be used in a normative or descriptive sense. When used in a normative sense, according to Gert, morality refers to a set of universal rules for conduct that, under a set of tenable assumptions, all rational beings would propose as the basis for guiding the conduct of all moral actors.³ On the other hand, it refers to significant attitudes of an individual when used in a descriptive manner. According to Kwasi Wiredu, morality is ubiquitous and fundamental to human culture. Although morality is the observance of laws for the peaceful adjustment of a person’s interests to those of others in society, it does not refer to the compliance with the rules for the peaceful adjustment of interests which is motivated by a creative and sympathetic identification with the interests of others.⁴

Similar to the above, Paul Aluko defines morality as the characteristic of human actions by which we categorize them as right or wrong, good or evil, and which can be either subjective or objective depending on whether it takes into account or ignores the individual characteristics of the act’s performer.⁵ It is important to keep in mind that morality can be applied to a variety of contexts, including religion, culture, and tradition. However, the religious component is the study’s main focus. Religious morality is a man’s relationship with God in which he upholds moral principles meant to direct his behavior in public. Therefore, morality in this case refers to how we perceive human behavior and how it can be classified as either acceptable or immoral in light of accepted moral standards.

National Integration

Integration literally refers to bringing disparate elements together into a cohesive whole by removing tensions and discrepancies. The term implies that there is a diversity of religions and ethnicities, and that these distinctions give rise to the problem of unification. Therefore, national integration is the process of integrating various cultural, religious, and social groupings into a pre-existing national unity.⁶ In this situation, national integration is the process that creates a just social unity, giving each citizen a sense of belonging, a satisfactory level of decision-making participation, and a fair share of the resources of the society that are necessary for a decent and respectable standard of living.

James O’Connel and Paul Beckett collaborates much more soundly by explaining that national integration comprises of collaborative interrelated efforts to promote certain mutual interests, spanning from concerns of

welfare, order, security, and defense.⁷ In light of this, an integrated nation is one that exhibits strong cooperation between various religious groups for the good of all its residents. It entails the sharedness of a nation's value markers, such as its language and shared experiences, as well as progress made toward creating unity and togetherness among the citizenry.

Religious Role in Shaping Morality in Nigeria

Religion is a significant phenomenon in contemporary Nigeria because it has an impact on all facets of Nigerian society and because its practices are taking over people's lives. Nigeria is an example of a plural society that is divided into many religious groups. There are many different religions in Nigeria, but the three most prevalent are African religion, Islam, and Christianity. Due to their huge adherent bases, Christianity and Islam are the two biggest religions in Nigeria. Being the two main religions in Nigeria, Christianity and Islam have demonstrated intense political rivalry. This is due to how seriously Nigerians take their faith. Religious institutions therefore have a part to play in combating immorality in Nigeria. The high level of immorality in the nation demonstrates that religious institutions have fallen short in their responsibility to promote moral principles in their adherents. Therefore, religious leaders must accept the challenge of teaching morals to their flock.

Promoting Uniformity of Behaviours

The belief in God as the Ultimate Source of Life, the creator, sustainer, and preserver of all things is one of the shared values among Nigeria's three major religions. Additionally, each of these religions shares common ideals that, if upheld, can promote religious homogeneity and racial integration. These values encompass notions of right and wrong, rewards and punishments, responsibility before God, notions of the afterlife and judgment, and others. Religion has brought Nigerians joy through transformation and progress, but it has also led to many concerns and tensions among the population. In this instance, Lemuel Odeh points out that religious difficulties have thrown Nigeria into a maelstrom of issues that are having increasing repercussions for the country's integration. Religious crises have plagued Nigeria as a country on a regular basis since 1980. Lack of religious tolerance has resulted in ongoing religious conflicts, which have given rise to numerous militias in the nation that engage in acts such as rioting, sabotage, and assassination, among other things.⁸ For example, suicide terrorist techniques were used by Boko Haram and ISWAP in their attacks, which resulted in a large number of fatalities in the nation.

While this is happening, religious institutions in Nigeria have a responsibility to shape the character of their followers by instilling a sense of social worth, respect for human life, and consideration for others' feelings. This will create uniformity that is important for national cohesion. This can be accomplished through comprehending the shared principles shared by African religions, Christianity, and Islam. Whatever their differences, all of these religions can foster a feeling of community among their adherents by urging them to show their love for God and for one another via charitable endeavors, social solidarity, and other acts that serve to maintain the social order.

Teaching Moral Living

It is pertinent to state unequivocally that religion can greatly aid in national integration by promoting moral values that are sorely lacking in modern society. This is because morality is seen as the byproduct or fruit of religion in Nigeria.⁹ Religion provides guidance on how to resist greed, lust, and hatred via moral strength and courage. It also guarantees values and gives life meaning. Therefore, it is the holy duty of Christianity, Islam, and African religion to advance a better and more harmonious way of life for the populace. National integration requires religious moral ideals that are rooted in religion texts, traditions, and beliefs. These virtues include kindness, compassion, mercy, generosity, dedication to duty, brotherliness, peace, love, justice, tolerance, obedience, self-control, prudence, courage, wisdom, goodness, and others. The moral values that birthed by religion enables people to make moral judgements according to divine ethics and justice. Therefore, religion

morality serves as a guide for building a community where people can live in harmony and uphold what is decent and just.¹⁰ As a result, religious organizations have a responsibility to instill moral values in their followers.

Leading the Way for Moral Living

The only institutions that offer a flawless way of life that is based on heavenly principles and helps people to develop morality are religious institutions. It is the duty of these organizations, such as churches, mosques, schools, and others, to instill moral ideals through music, sermons, special seminars, and workshops, among other methods. Religious organizations should also speak out, act practically, and set an example for their followers by upholding moral principles. Similarly, by steadfastly combating immorality, homosexuality, corruption, and other issues that can divide people in the nation, religious organizations can serve as a unifying force. Religious organizations have a duty to guide people in the right direction by modeling moral behavior in homes, communities, societies, and governments. They are the guardians of morality. In essence, religious organizations must take up the role of the way and fly the morality flag high.¹¹ Therefore, all of Nigeria's religions must work together to encourage their followers to take steps toward the actualization of national integration. Each of these religions in Nigeria must actively impart moral principles that will serve as a guide for people's behavior, character, and attitude, forming their personalities and values and fostering national integration.

Moral Values, Essential for National Integration

It is important to keep in mind that the application of religious moral values by various religious institutions and followers can considerably foster harmony, interreligious harmony, and tolerance, which permit efficient national integration in all ramifications. The following is a discussion of some moral virtues that are crucial for national integration, such as peace, tolerance, understanding, justice, and self-control.

Peace

In the course of human history, peace has long been seen as a valuable phenomenon and is even one of the core teachings of the major world religions. According to Muhammad Anjum, the word "peace" denotes calmness, a lack of hostilities, or the absence of war. It is a state of security or order and reconciliation after strife.¹² This definition focuses on the absence of war, violence, terrorism and unrest. The Yoruba conception of peace, however, extends beyond these oppositions. *Àláfíà* is the Yoruba word for peace. According to Babatunde Adebola, "The word *Àláfíà* encompasses the idea that all is well in all parts of life." In this condition, peace encompasses more than just the absence of conflict or turbulence; it also refers to one's mental calm, physical well-being, social harmony and unity, and the existence of both human and other supernatural beings.¹³ In Hebrew and Judaism, this concept is known as *shalom*. Along with reflecting a peaceful approach, avoiding arguments, and fostering tranquillity in society interactions, it also involves wellness and healing in interpersonal and national relationships. Many religions in the world place great value on peace and promote coexistence and peaceful living. Al-Qur'an, and the Bible both contain teachings and exhortations for peace. Peace, in the opinion of Nicholas Okpe, is a fundamental moral principle that is based on the idea that life is meant to foster good relationships with people through consensual decision-making. It is the condition in which a person strives to live in harmony with himself, his neighbor, and his surroundings.¹⁴

In the Nigerian setting, a series of intrigues are churlishly relegating peace. This is demonstrated by the unsettling animosity that certain Muslims and Christians have toward one another, which prevents them from coexisting peacefully, developing prestigious socio-political structures, and using peace as a compass for national unification. It is important to note that peace is a gift and virtue that is essential for national integration. Therefore, religious institutions in Nigeria must cooperate to advance peace since true integration cannot occur in the absence of peace.

Tolerance

The ability to recognize and appreciate the views and practices of others is what is meant by tolerance. It is a moral quality that permits freedom of action. Building national cohesion and coexistence requires tolerance. Accepting and upholding the fundamental rights and religious convictions of individuals and groups whose viewpoints differ from one's own is referred to as exercising religious tolerance. Since tolerance is essential to achieving national integration, it is the duty of all religious organizations to practically instruct their followers to practice it in both their words and deeds. The capacity to deal with opposing viewpoints without raising grievances or resorting to violence is what it means to be tolerant. Religious extremists have exacerbated intolerance in the nation, which has severely hampered its integration. Therefore, there is a need for tolerance especially among the adherents of the various religions in the country.¹⁵ Tolerance for religion refers to respecting another person's right to hold beliefs that differ from one's own. It entails abstaining from treating people who adhere to other religions unfairly or with prejudice. In order to promote national integration, all religions in Nigeria have a duty to instill in their adherents an understanding of and respect for the religious beliefs of others.

Understanding

An understanding is an accord of opinion or emotion; it is a cordial or pleasant relationship. Understanding the variations in religious beliefs is necessary to achieve national integration. Many of the issues presently plaguing Nigeria are caused by the fact that the country's supposedly deeply religious population are either unable to comprehend other religions or do understand them but prefer their own to rule over others.

Justice

Justice is a concept of moral rightness derived from religion, natural law, ethics, reason, law, and other sources. It entails acting in a just, fair, and upright manner. Nigerian religions have a duty to advance the moral value of justice. National integration depends on social and political justice. Therefore, it is crucial for religious organizations in Nigeria to spread the message of justice as a moral principle through their varied teachings and exhortations.

Self-control

Self-control is the capacity to restrain one's desires in order to accomplish organizational goals. It can also be described as self-imposed norms and constraints motivated by a desire that outweighs the alternatives and maintained in accordance with a set of objectives and commitment required by the planned outcome.¹⁶ Self-control as a moral virtue permits one to resist immoral financial and sexual temptations, to always speak the truth, and to never be caught lying about anything. According to Psalm 15:2-5, such a person is "He whose walk is spotless, who performs what is just, who speaks the truth from his heart." Who does not despise a wicked man but honors those who fear the LORD, who keeps his word even when it hurts, who lends money without charging interest, and who refuses to take a bribe against the defenseless; who has no slander on his tongue. Self-control is a virtue that makes it possible to stay away from immoral behaviors like prejudice, oppression, corruption, and other similar behaviors and instead concentrate on what is right for everyone.

Respect for Human Life

The idea that human life should be respected emanate from the belief that God made man in His likeness. Respect for human life is an important moral principle that is necessary for fostering mutual understanding, trust, and respect for one another's views and behaviors in order to promote national integration. Additionally, this morality would encourage collaboration in the family, classroom, workplace, and other social or cultural settings among followers of diverse religions. Also, it will allow people from all religious backgrounds to work together to advance humanitarian activities, such as aiding the sick, the impoverished, and those in need, while also fostering religious unity in Nigeria's multireligious society.¹⁷

Conclusion

This study has examined the role of religion in shaping morality towards national integration. It was stated that religion has a crucial role in fostering national cohesion by encouraging and instilling moral values in its adherents. The rationale is that since religion is the custodian of morality, as such have the obligation to morally teach, guide and lead the followers in the way through which they would demonstrate character, conduct and attitude that reflect good morality in the homes, families, societies, and governments. The study also identified useful moral virtues relevant for national integration. This includes respect for human life, peace, tolerance, understanding, and self-control. In this case, religions institutions have a divine duty to impart these values to its adherents. Therefore, it is recommended that all religious institutions in Nigeria must come together to build a common platform to curb the recurrent issues of moral crises manifesting in different form such as intolerance, corruption, fanaticism, idleness, lack of respect for human life and dignity, hatred, lust, greed, to promote peace, understanding, tolerance, self-discipline which are relevant for national integration.

Endnotes

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